

Tables used to build Figure 1 from paper "The Nurse Rostering Problem: Recent Advances and Future Perspectives"

Laura-Maria Cornei^{1*} and Mihaela-Elena Breabăn¹

^{1*}Computer Science, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University, General Berthelot 16, Iași, 700483, Romania.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): laura.cornei@info.uaic.ro, cornei.laura10@gmail.com;

Contributing authors: mihaela.breaban@info.uaic.ro;

Tables 1 and 2 contain information about the collected state-of-the-art nurse rostering papers, analyzed to build Figure 1 from paper "The Nurse Rostering Problem: Recent Advances and Future Perspectives". The works are divided into non-ML and ML approaches. The data is available under license CC BY 4.0.

Table 1. State-of-the-art non-ML techniques for solving the Nurse Rostering Problem

Type	Techniques (purpose)	Paper
MO	Network flow optimization (solution search)	The emergency department physician rostering problem obtaining equitable solutions via network optimization [6]
MO	Branch & Cut (solution search)	A stochastic integer programming approach to reserve staff scheduling with preferences [26]
H, MO	PDA & SAA (solution search) H (sampling strategy of SAA, additional bounds for PDA)	An online stochastic algorithm for a dynamic nurse scheduling problem [19]
H, MO	H (initial solutions), B&P (solution search), DP (speed up search)	A branch-and-price approach for the nurse rostering problem with multiple units [15]
Meta-H	DO (solutions' search)	Dragonfly algorithm application for solving the nurse scheduling problem [4]
Meta-H	PSO & GA (solutions' search)	An Intelligent Optimization Strategy for Medical Doctor Rostering Using Hybrid Genetic Algorithm - Particle Swarm Optimization in Malaysian Public Hospital [35]

Meta-H, MO	GA, Branch & Cut (solutions' search)	Maximizing Shift Preference for Nurse Rostering Schedule Using Integer Linear Programming and Genetic Algorithm [21]
Meta-H, MO	Branch & Cut (initial solutions), BPSO (solutions' improvement)	A mat-heuristic based solution approach for an extended nurse rostering problem with skills and units [33]
H, Meta-H	H (initial solutions, transitions in ILS), Elitist-AS (global search), ILS (solution improvement)	Hybrid Elitist-Ant System for Nurse-Rostering Problem [16]
H, Meta-H	H (initial solution, transitions in SA), SA (solution improvement)	Solving the static INRC-II nurse rostering problem by simulated annealing based on large neighborhoods [7]
H, Meta-H	VNS (solution search), H (transitions in VNS, aggregating scores within the fitness function)	A novel fuzzy meta-heuristic approach in nurse rostering problem [31]
H, Hyper-H	H (initial solution, low-level heuristics in SSHH), SSHH (solution search)	A hyper-heuristic approach based upon a hidden Markov model for the multi-stage nurse rostering problem [17]
H, Meta-H	H(initial solution, transitions in VNS), VNS (solution improvement)	A New Two-stage Variable Neighborhood Search Algorithm for the Nurse Rostering Problem [1]
H, Meta-H	H (initial solutions), HS (global search), SA (improvement of best HS solution)	Annealing Harmony Search Algorithm to Solve the Nurse Rostering Problem [14]
H, Meta-H	MCTS & HC (initial solution), ILS (solution improvement), H (transitions in ILS)	A 2-Stage Approach for the Nurse Rostering Problem [11]
H, Meta-H	H (initial solutions, operators in NSGA-II), NSGA-II (solutions' improvement)	A preventive-reactive approach for nurse scheduling considering absenteeism and nurses' preferences [25]
H, Meta-H	H (initial solution, transitions in ALNS), ALNS (solution improvement)	Adaptive large neighborhood search for a personnel task scheduling problem with task selection and parallel task assignments [12]
H, Meta-H	H (initial solutions, local search in GA, operators in GA, decoding mechanism), GA (solutions' improvement)	A genetic algorithm for the personnel task rescheduling problem with time preemption [5]
H, Meta-H	H (initial solutions), GA (global search), VNS (solutions' improvements)	Enhancing Nurse Scheduling with User Preferences Hybrid Genetic Algorithm and Variable Neighbourhood Search Approach [3]
H, Meta-H, MO	H (initial solution, transitions in ILS), H & SO (problem reduction) ILS (solution search), Branch & Cut (determining final solution)	Three-phase method for Nurse Rostering [13]
H, Meta-H, MO	H, Branch & Cut (initial solution, shaking), SA (solution improvement)	A hybrid fix-and-optimize and simulated annealing approaches for nurse rostering problem [32]
H, Meta-H, MO	H (initial solutions, operators in BCO), BCO (solutions' improvement), Branch & Cut (recreate operator in BCO)	A hybrid integer programming and artificial bee colony algorithm for staff scheduling in call centers [34]
H, Meta-H, MO	Branch & Cut (initial solution) LNS (solution improvement), H (transitions in LNS)	Nurse rostering with fatigue modeling [18]

Table 2. State-of-the-art ML-based methods for solving the Nurse Rostering Problem

Type	Techniques (purpose)	Paper
DL, H	HTS (solution search using Probability-Penalty-Strategy), DNN (estimating the distance towards an optimal solution)	[8]
DL, H	H (initial solution, transitions), DNN (heuristic selection), RNN (repair operator)	[10]
DL, H, MO	H (initial solution, transitions), DNN (heuristic selection), MIP (repair operator)	[9]
DL, Meta-H, MO	H (initial solution, transitions in LNS), LNS (solution improvement), GNN (destroy operator in LNS), MIP (repair operator in LNS)	[24]
ML (DL)	RL (solution search), GNN (learning the policy)	[27]
DL, Meta-H, H	H (initial solution, transitions & perturbation mechanism in ILS), ILS (solution search), TS (local search), DQN (heuristic selection inside TS)	[37]
DL, Meta-H, H	H (initial solution), TS (solution search), DQN (heuristic selection)	[36]
ML, Meta-H	ML model (initial solution), SA (solution improvement)	[28]
Hyper-H, Meta-H, ML	Hyper-H (solution search), RL (low-level heuristic selection), SA (move acceptance criterion)	[22]
ML, MO	ML (reducing solutions' space), MIP (solution search)	[29]
DL, MO	DNN (reducing solutions' space), MIP (solution search)	[30]
ML, MO	ML (reducing solutions' space), MIP (solution search)	[20]
DL, MO	GNN (solution search), MIP (solution improvement)	[23]
ML (DL)	ML (reducing solutions' space), DL (solution search)	[2]

List of abbreviations

ML	Machine Learning	Hyper-H	Hyper-Heuristic
DL	Deep Learning	HTS	Heuristic Tree Search
RL	Reinforcement Learning	SSHH	Sequence based Selection Hyper-Heuristic
DP	Dynamic Programming	MCTS	Monte Carlo Tree Search
MO	Mathematical Optimization	HC	Hill Climbing
(M)I(L)P	(Mixed) Integer (Linear) Programming	SA	Simulated Annealing
SAA	Sample Average Approximation	(A)LNS	(Adaptive) Large Neighborhood Search
PDA	Primal Dual Algorithm	ILS	Iterated Local Search
NFO	Network Flow Optimization	VNS	Variable Neighborhood Search
B&P	Branch & Price	TS	Tabu Search
SO	Subgradient Optimization	HS	Harmony Search
DNN	Deep Neural Network	BCO	Bee Colony Optimization
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network	DO	Dragonfly Optimization
DQN	Deep Q-Network	GA	Genetic Algorithm
GNN	Graph Neural Network	NSGA-II	Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II
H	Heuristic	(B)PSO	(Binary) Particle Swarm Optimization
Math-H	Math-Heuristic		
Meta-H	Meta-Heuristic		

References

- [1] Abdelghany, Yahia et al. A new two-stage variable neighborhood search algorithm for the nurse rostering problem. *RAIRO-Operations Research*, 55(2):673–687, 2021.
- [2] Aibin, Chen et al. Federated learning framework for nurse scheduling to lower fatigue levels of nurses. In *2025 International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC)*, pages 340–344. IEEE, 2025.
- [3] Atoyebi, Abayomi-Alli et al. Enhancing nurse scheduling with user preferences: Hybrid genetic algorithm and variable neighbourhood search approach. In *2024 IEEE 5th International Conference on Electro-Computing Technologies for Humanity (NIGERCON)*, pages 1–5. IEEE, 2024.
- [4] Ayoughi, Zhang et al. Dragonfly algorithm application for solving the nurse scheduling problem. In *2024 International Conference on Computing, Networking and Communications (ICNC)*, pages 39–43. IEEE Computer Society, 2024.
- [5] Borgonjon and Maenhout. A genetic algorithm for the personnel task rescheduling problem with time preemption. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 238:121868, 2024.
- [6] Capanera, Visintin et al. The emergency department physician rostering problem: obtaining equitable solutions via network optimization. *Flexible Services and Manufacturing Journal*, pages 1–44, 2021.
- [7] Ceschia, Guido et al. Solving the static inrc-ii nurse rostering problem by simulated annealing based on large neighborhoods. *Annals of Operations Research*, 288(1):95–113, 2020.
- [8] Chen, De Causmaecker et al. Deep neural networked assisted tree search for the personnel rostering problem. In *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on the Practice and Theory of Automated Timetabling-PATAT*, volume 2, 2021.
- [9] Chen, De Causmaecker et al. A combined mixed integer programming and deep neural network-assisted heuristics algorithm for the nurse rostering problem. *Applied Soft Computing*, 136:109919, 2023.
- [10] Chen, Dou et al. Neural networked-assisted method for the nurse rostering problem. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 171:108430, 2022.
- [11] Goh, Sabar et al. A 2-stage approach for the nurse rostering problem. *IEEE Access*, 10:69591–69604, 2022.
- [12] Gutjahr, Parragh et al. Adaptive large neighborhood search for a personnel task scheduling problem with task selection and parallel task assignments. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2302.04494*, 2023.
- [13] Haddadi. Three-phase method for nurse rostering. *International Journal of Management Science and Engineering Management*, 14(3):193–205, 2019.

- [14] Hadwan. Annealing harmony search algorithm to solve the nurse rostering problem. *Computers, Materials & Continua*, 71(3), 2022.
- [15] Hu, He et al. A branch-and-price approach for the nurse rostering problem with multiple units. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 198:110629, 2023.
- [16] Jaradat, Al-Badareen et al. Hybrid elitist-ant system for nurse-rostering problem. *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences*, 31(3):378–384, 2019.
- [17] Kheiri, Gretsista et al. A hyper-heuristic approach based upon a hidden markov model for the multi-stage nurse rostering problem. *Computers & Operations Research*, 130:105221, 2021.
- [18] Klyve, Senthoran et al. Nurse rostering with fatigue modelling: Incorporating a validated sleep model with biological variations in nurse rostering. *Health Care Management Science*, 26(1):21–45, 2023.
- [19] Legrain, Omer et al. An online stochastic algorithm for a dynamic nurse scheduling problem. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 285(1):196–210, 2020.
- [20] Liu, Wang et al. Learning-based algorithm for physician scheduling for emergency departments under time-varying demand and patient return. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 128:107477, 2024.
- [21] Mohd Razali, Tamilarasan et al. Maximizing shift preference for nurse rostering schedule using integer linear programming and genetic algorithm. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science & Applications*, 16(5), 2025.
- [22] Muklason, Kusuma et al. Solving nurse rostering optimization problem using reinforcement learning-simulated annealing with reheating hyper-heuristics algorithm. *Procedia Computer Science*, 234:486–493, 2024.
- [23] Nguyen, Truong et al. Faster, larger, stronger: Optimally solving employee scheduling problems with graph neural networks. In *International Symposium on Information and Communication Technology*, pages 141–151. Springer, 2024.
- [24] Oberweger, Raidl et al. A learning large neighborhood search for the staff rostering problem. In *International Conference on Integration of Constraint Programming, Artificial Intelligence, and Operations Research*, pages 300–317. Springer, 2022.
- [25] Otero-Caicedo, Casas et al. A preventive–reactive approach for nurse scheduling considering absenteeism and nurses’ preferences. *Operations Research for Health Care*, 38:100389, 2023.
- [26] Perreault-Lafleur, Carvalho et al. A stochastic integer programming approach to reserve staff scheduling with preferences. *International Transactions in Operational Research*, 32(1):289–313, 2025.
- [27] Platten, Macfarlane et al. Automated personnel scheduling with reinforcement learning and graph neural networks. 2022.

- [28] Quak. A novel hybrid machine learning metaheuristic approach to create nurse rosters in a dutch hospital. Master's thesis, University of Twente, 2023.
- [29] Rastgar-Amini, Aloise et al. Data mining-driven shift enumeration for accelerating the solution of large-scale personnel scheduling problems. *ACM Transactions on Evolutionary Learning*, 2024.
- [30] Rastgar-Amini, Contardo et al. Learning to enumerate shifts for large-scale flexible personnel scheduling problems. *Journal of Scheduling*, pages 1–19, 2025.
- [31] Simić, Corchado et al. A novel fuzzy metaheuristic approach in nurse rostering problem. *Logic Journal of the IGPL*, 28(4):583–595, 2020.
- [32] Turhan and Bilgen. A hybrid fix-and-optimize and simulated annealing approaches for nurse rostering problem. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 145:106531, 2020.
- [33] Turhan and Bilgen. A mat-heuristic based solution approach for an extended nurse rostering problem with skills and units. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, 82:101300, 2022.
- [34] Xu and Wang. A hybrid integer programming and artificial bee colony algorithm for staff scheduling in call centers. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 171:108312, 2022.
- [35] Zainudin, Hasan et al. An intelligent optimization strategy for medical doctor rostering using hybrid genetic algorithm-particle swarm optimization in malaysian public hospital. *Malaysian Journal of Fundamental and Applied Sciences*, 21(1):1642–1653, 2025.
- [36] Zhang, Yang et al. Multi-agent deep q-network-based metaheuristic algorithm for nurse rostering problem. *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, 87:101547, 2024.
- [37] Zhang, Zhu et al. Deep q-network-based neighborhood tabu search for nurse rostering problem. *Available at SSRN 4635872*, 2023.